

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF BERYLLIUM-ALUMINUM COMPOSITES

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Introduction

Beryllium exhibits an attractive combination of properties, including a very low density and high specific modulus. Unalloyed beryllium is used in many applications, including weapons, spacecraft, nuclear reactor reflector segments, neutron sources, windows for x-ray tubes and radiation detection discs, precision instruments and mirrors. However, its relatively low ductility at room temperature has limited its use in many structural applications such as in the aerospace industry, where its high specific strength and stiffness would be very advantageous.

Lockheed Missiles and Space Company undertook an extensive study of the beryllium-aluminum system, and by 1964 had developed an alloy known as "Lockalloy." This alloy generally contains 38 w% aluminum and is produced as extrusions and sheet hot-rolled from extruded bar stock. Lockalloy combines the ductile properties of aluminum with the high strength, low density, and stiffness of beryllium. It has excellent thermal characteristics and also exhibits good formability and machining characteristics, resulting in its use in several aerospace applications.

Various other alloys based on aluminum and beryllium have been developed to take advantage of the high specific stiffness of the Be with the ductility and ease of fabrication of Al. Alloys ranging from 10-75% beryllium have been discussed in the literature.

A study of one such alloy currently under development, Be-50Al with additions of silver, is presented in this work. The material in this study has been rapidly solidified and hot isostatically pressed. According to the Be-Al phase diagram, there is very limited solubility of Be in Al; 0.3 ± 0.1 at.% at the eutectic temperature of 644 °C, and less than 0.007 at.% solubility of Al in Be. The microstructures produced thus far can be thought of as three dimensional inter-penetrating composites, where both the ductile (Al) and brittle (Be) phases are continuous. Because of liquid phase separation, to be discussed later, the resulting microstructures can be described as a three-dimensional interpenetrating composite, in which both phases are continuous. The size of the components in this "composite" are on the scale of 1 micron.

Properties of beryllium

In order to explain the deformation behavior of beryllium-aluminum composites, it is important to understand the properties and deformation mechanisms which occur in

Table 1: Properties of several pure metals

Property	Be	Al	Cu	Mg	Ti
Atomic Weight	9.012	26.98	63.54	24.31	47.9
Density (Mg/m^3)	1.848	2.700	8.93	1.738	4.507
Melting point ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	1290	660	1085	650	1668
Thermal expansion ($\mu\text{m/m}\cdot\text{K}$)	11.6	23.6	16.5	25.2	8.41
Specific heat ($\text{J/kg}\cdot\text{K}$)	1886	900	494	1025	522
Thermal conductivity ($\text{W/m}\cdot\text{K}$)	190	247	398	418	11.4

Figure 1: Specific modulus of some engineering materials

monolithic beryllium. Shown in Table 1 are the physical properties of several pure metals [1]. Of these metals, Be has the lowest atomic weight and a lower density than Ti or even Al. Its melting point is relatively high, indicative of its high elastic modulus. Its thermal expansion coefficient is relatively low, making it dimensionally stable during temperature changes. This is an important feature, especially during composite processing.

Figure 1 depicts the specific modulus (elastic modulus divided by density) of some engineering materials compared to that of pure Be [2]. The specific modulus of Be is very attractive when compared to Al alloys, Cu alloys, steels, Ni alloys and even Ti alloys. The problem is that pure Be is relatively brittle at room temperature, requiring special precautions when using it for structural applications.

Beryllium has a hexagonal close packed structure, which is an **ABAB** stacking of close packed planes, shown in Figure 2, with the vectors c and a as labeled. Be has a c/a ratio lower than ideal, which means that the six neighboring atoms outside of the basal plane are somewhat closer than those within the basal plane. In all other hexagonal metals, low c/a ratios provide primary slip on the prism plane, as expected. In Be, however, the primary slip mode is basal slip. This only represents two independent slip modes. For arbitrary three-dimensional deformation, the von Mises criterion requires five independent slip modes. The only slip system in Be involving dislocations with a Burgers vector inclined to the basal plane is the second order pyramidal plane, which provides five independent slip modes. This is difficult to activate at room temperature, however it does play a role at slightly elevated temperatures, leading to a brittle-to-ductile transition in

Figure 2: Beryllium crystal structure

Be.

Beryllium is brittle at room temperature for a number of reasons, primarily, its unusual atomic bonding characteristics: its very low ratio of bulk to shear modulus, its anomalously low Poissons ratio of 0.03, and its anomalous slip behavior, described earlier. Secondly, it exhibits a large anisotropy in its critical resolved shear stress, leading to the predominance of basal slip. Finally, the basal plane, its “easy” slip system, is also its “easy” cleavage plane, which means that Be fractures predominantly by basal plane cleavage [3].

Development of beryllium-aluminum alloys

The possibilities of combining Be with Al, in order to take advantage of the good ductility of Al have been recognized for many years. By 1964, Lockheed Missiles and Space Company introduced Localalloy, a powder metallurgy product consisting of Be with 38 w% Al. This composition was chosen because it gave a rule-of-mixtures elastic modulus of the composite equal to that of steel. This was the first Be-Al product to reach commercial development, and was successfully used in military applications such as extruded skin stiffeners for missiles.

Current research includes optimizing the Be-Al ratios for different applications, examining the role of ternary additions such as Ag and Mg to improve the properties of the Al, and looking at the effects of various thermo-mechanical processing conditions on the microstructure and resulting properties of the composite.

The Be-Al phase diagram, shown in Figure 3, is a simple eutectic with no compounds. There is little or no solubility of Be in Al, or of Al in Be. The size and morphology of the resulting two phase alloy therefore depends on the solidification rate and processing history.

Various researchers [4] have found a submerged metastable liquid miscibility gap in the Be-Al system, depicted on Figure 3. This can be used to produce liquid phase separation, resulting in unique microstructures at rapid rates of solidification. As depicted in Figure 4, spinodal decomposition occurs between the inflection points on the free energy versus composition plot. Within this range, there is no nucleation barrier to the separation of phases, and the resulting phases are continuous. Various researchers have

Figure 3: Depiction of beryllium-aluminum three-dimensional interpenetrating composite morphology

shown that the optimum ratio of Be-Al may occur between 40 and 60 w% Al. The resulting microstructure, depicted in Figure 3 can be described as a three-dimensional interpenetrating composite.

Composite processing

Fifty weight percent beryllium-aluminum alloys containing 2.5, 3, and 4 w% Ag were fabricated. Various others have used Mg, which is similarly soluble in Al. Ag forms a compound with Be, AgBe_2 , but it was expected that this compound would be avoided under rapid solidification. The powder was produced by a centrifugal atomization process, which resulted in a very fine microstructure, characterized as a three-dimensional interpenetrating composite, where both phases are continuous. By etching away the Al phase, it was shown that both phases are indeed continuous.

The alloys in this study were produced by hot isostatically pressing powder made by centrifugal atomization. The centrifugal atomization process has been investigated for producing beryllium and beryllium alloy powders.¹ A first-generation Pratt & Whitney experimental centrifugal atomizer was utilized to produce about 30 kg of beryllium and beryllium alloy powders. The centrifugal atomization process involves induction melting a metal charge under argon in a crucible and directing the molten metal through a nozzle onto the surface of a rapidly spinning disk. The liquid metal is mechanically atomized into finely divided droplets at the periphery of the spinning disk. The droplets are solidified in flight in the atomizing chamber by heat transfer to helium gas which also carries the powder product into a cyclone separator. The centrifugal atomization process produces spherical powder particles ranging in size from 5–200 microns with solidification rates on the order of 10^4 – 10^7 °C/s. The powder is then screened, canned, and hot isostatically pressed to 100% density at 590°C under 30 ksi. Alloys with various Ag additions have been fabricated to examine the effects of Ag content. Powders with 2.5, 3, and 4% Ag have been produced and hot isostatically pressed. Only the 2.5% alloy has been successfully rolled.

¹This process was first developed under the National Aerospace Program, and then under a Cooperative Research Agreement with Pratt & Whitney

Figure 4: Spinodal decomposition

Figure 5: Microstructure of powder particles

Figure 5 is the microstructure of the powder particles under backscattered SEM imaging, which enhances the contrast between the Be and Al. It is evident that the phases have a range in dimension, due to differences in cooling rates. Slower cooling rates result in the expected eutectic equilibrium microstructure of Be dendrites in an Al matrix. More rapid solidification results in liquid phase separation, leading to continuous phases, in the interpenetrating morphology described previously.

The microstructure and grain size is fairly stable even after a long-term high-temperature anneal. Figures 6(a) and 6(b) show the microstructure after an anneal at 550°C after 2 and 25 days, respectively.

Mechanical testing

Tensile tests were performed on the Be-47.5Al-2.5Ag alloy which was rolled into sheet, the results of which are listed in Table 2. These samples were given three different

Figure 6: Microstructure before and after a long-term anneal at 550°C

Table 2: Tensile tests of rolled Be-47.5Al-2.5Ag sheet

Sample	Condition	Yield MPa (ksi)	Ult MPa (ksi)	Elong. (%)
A	Quench, 550 °C, 1 hr	356 (51.7)	427 (61.9)	6.6
B	Quench, 550 °C, 1 hr	358 (51.9)	430 (62.3)	9.6
C	Anneal, 550 °C, 1 hr	356 (51.7)	393 (57.0)	4.8
D	Anneal, 550 °C, 1 hr	354 (51.4)	399 (57.9)	6.3
E	Q-Age, 175 °C, 16 hrs	400 (58.0)	455 (66.0)	10.6
F	Q-Age, 175 °C, 16 hrs	399 (57.9)	458 (66.4)	9.1

heat treatment conditions. It is evident that the highest strengths as well as the highest elongations were achieved with material which was given a long-term low temperature age: 175°C for 16 hours. These results compare quite favorably with properties of commercially available beryllium-aluminum alloys.

The fracture surfaces of all the tests performed were ductile in nature, showing evidence of substantial plastic deformation. Figures 7(a) and 7(b) are micrographs of fracture surfaces from two of these tensile tests. Evidence of precipitation of Ag particles is also observed on the sample in the annealed condition (Figure 7(b)).

Further tests were performed to examine the effects of aging on the mechanical properties. Compression tests were performed on the Be-47.5Al-2.5Ag alloy under various heat treatment conditions. The results are shown in Figure 8. This is a plot of compression strength versus aging time and temperature, showing that the higher temperature aging for shorter times produced the best results. Initial TEM evaluations indicate that compound particles form, but appear to have a larger lattice parameter than an Ag₂Al phase.

Additional studies on the effects of aging on the hardness of these Be-Al-Ag composites have also been performed, the results of which shall be reported elsewhere.

Concluding remarks

Mechanical tests on Be-Al-Ag alloy samples produced from centrifugally atomized powders have shown improved mechanical properties with evidence of precipitation hard-

(a) As quenched

(b) Annealed

Figure 7: Fracture surfaces from tensile tests

Figure 8: Effect of aging on compression strength

ening. It is evident that this composite exhibited substantial elongation, (relative to pure Be) with the quenched and aged sample showing the greatest elongation.

Further work needs to be done to fully understand the mechanical behavior of this material. The goal of this future study will be to determine the fracture and deformation characteristics of this material. The first issue is to determine the relative importance of microcracking (associated with the Be phase) and plastic deformation (of the Al and/or Be) on the relatively large amount of elongation exhibited by this material.

A second issue, which encompasses many others, is to examine the effects of the scale of this microstructure. It is important to determine the thermo-mechanical processes necessary to control the microstructure, or the size and distribution of the components within the composite, in order to maximize its mechanical properties. This requires studies in thermo-mechanical processing of the alloys and studies of the initial solidification of the alloys. Due to the complexities inherent in this material, it is difficult to quantify the dimensions of the microstructure needed to optimize its mechanical properties. For example, the current microstructure, with components having dimensions on the order of 1 micron, may impart too much constraint on the aluminum phase for it to provide adequate ductility. Micromechanical modeling and characterization will be used to provide direction for materials processing and microstructure control.

References

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